

An Empirical Study of the Correlation between Non-Oil Export Growth and Foreign Direct Investment – A Case Study of Nigeria Economy Within 2000 To 2023

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ABSTRACT

This paper stand to unveil the dynamic relationship between Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and non-oil exports in Nigeria, within the context of economic diversification and sustainable development. Despite Nigeria's rich endowment of natural resources, its heavy reliance on oil exports has led to vulnerability to external shocks, limited economic diversification, and fiscal instability. In the bid to correct economic instability problem, successive governments have introduced several reforms and also established different institutions aimed at boosting non-oil exports and attracting FDI into non-oil sectors through several economic strategies. This study employs different research analysis methods such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, Granger causality tests and Augmented Dickey-Fuller Stationarity Test to examine the annual time series secondary data collected from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) annual bulletin, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) annual report as well as World Bank annual reports within the periods of 2000 to 2023, thereby studying the relationship between FDI, non-oil exports, and GDP growth. The research findings reveal a weak positive correlation between FDI and non-oil exports ($r = 0.1802$), a moderate relationship between non-oil exports and GDP ($r = 0.4423$), and a stronger correlation between FDI and GDP ($r = 0.6850$) according to correlation coefficient, while Granger causality results indicate that FDI significantly predicts non-oil export performance ($p = 0.0455$), but not vice versa, suggesting that while FDI contributes to non-oil export capacity, non-oil exports have yet to attract meaningful FDI inflows as such the relationship is not mutual. Furthermore, no significant causal relationships were found between GDP and either FDI or non-oil exports, to further confirm previous tests the unit root test established that there is no long term relationship between the study variables as such using FDI to predict non-oil export movement is impossible for now, but FDI can slightly predict GDP movement. These results highlight the untapped potential of FDI in driving non-oil export diversification and emphasize the need for targeted policy reforms, improved infrastructure, and institutional strengthening to align FDI inflows with non-oil sector development. The study recommends sector-specific investment strategies, where the government pull is force towards growth of specific non-oil sectors such as Manufacturing sector, Agricultural sector, services sector to enhance and encourage absorptive capacity, and long-term policy consistency to enable proper implementation of the policy framework as key drivers of inclusive growth and economic transformation in Nigeria.

KEYWORDS:

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Non-oil exports, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Diversification, Correlation, infrastructural development

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria lies in the sub-Saharan region of West Africa on the latitude of 10°N and longitude 8°N. It is blessed with abundant natural resources from vegetation to solid minerals such as coal, iron ore, limestone, gold, silver, diamond, tin ore, columbite and zinc (Ministry of Mines and Steel, 2017) which is largely under-exploited as well as liquid minerals such as crude oil. These natural resources have been the mainstay of the country since its inception. The country initially depends on Agriculture as its main source of export and economic structure which was largely dominated by non-oil products such as groundnuts, palm kernel, palm oil, cocoa, rubber, cotton, coffee, copra, beniseed, hides and skin. Over 66% of total exports on the average were accounted for by these commodities, until the 1950s when oil was discovered in the country, which now led to the overdependence of the country on oil which resulted to about 90% of the foreign exchange export earnings of the country, which is about 70% of government revenue thereby resulting in currency appreciation, making other export sector less competitive and cause the neglect of non-oil sector such as agriculture and manufacturing sector whereby creating economic imbalance. The overreliance on oil exports exposed the nation to global oil price volatility, fiscal instability as well as limited economic diversification. In the bid to correct this challenge several governments have in their own way implemented various policies to check this over dependent issue such as the Operation Green Revolution introduced by Gen. Olusegun Obasanjo in the 1970s, the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) implemented by the then Gen Ibrahim Babangida administration in the 1980s and the further establishment of some government institutions such as Nigerian Export Promotion Council (NEPC) under Act No. 26 of 1976 (amended by Act No. 41 of 1988) while, Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission (NIPC) which was originally enacted in 1995 to encourage investor into the non-oil sector as well as promotion export of non-oil products. This initiative made the country to record increase of non-oil export products from 5.8 percent in 1986 to 8.6 percent in 1988, although the increase isn't steady but successive governments and policymakers have continuously implement policies to promote non-oil exports as a strategic pathway to economic sustainance, job creation and inclusive economic growth. In a way of achieving this objective the foreign direct investment (FDI) has emerged as the pipeline to export diversification and economic transformation. Although the total investment of a country which is the Gross investment in an economy comprises domestic and foreign investment. All things being equal, FDI is expected to contribute to the stock of capital in any economy. Therefore, our concentration is on the foreign direct investment. Foreign Direct Investment is considered as a process of transfer of technology or capital or both from other developed or other developing countries to developing or underdeveloped countries (Melnyk, Kubatko, and Pysarenko, 2014). This allows technological transfer, creation of employment opportunities as well as improved productivity of non-oil products, thereby resulting GDP increase, where the GDP of non-oil export sector includes agricultural products, metals, and fertilizers, with agricultural exports being a significant component and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Overall Growth expanding from ₦329.18 billion in 2000 to ₦2.344 trillion in 2023, even when a sudden spike occurred in 2014 with a figure of ₦2.964 trillion. This could be due to a rebasing of GDP calculations or data inconsistencies. This paper is to investigate the relationship between non-oil export growth and foreign direct investment for the country Nigeria as a special case for the studies. This sector covers all export that are not crude oil base. This sector serves as the working environment, while the foreign direct investment(FDI) is the tools that permits non-oil exports sector to exist in the

country. Theoretically FDI can serve as a catalyst for non-oil exports development by allowing increase productivity, introducing innovation, and facilitating integration into the global value chains. Therefore, an expanded non-oil export sector may attract FDI by signs of market potential, improved infrastructure and reduced economic risk through diversification. Despite Nigeria effort to attract FDI into the non-oil sector economic space through the introduction of various economic reforms such as trade liberalization, industrial revolution policies reform, establishment of special economic trade zones. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) growth record as significantly increased from ₦6.38 trillion in 2000 to ₦43.56 trillion in 2023, despite the decline in 2005 to ₦3.43 trillion, possibly due to global economic factors or domestic policy changes.

However, the relationship between these two indicators remain complex and inconsistent as factors such as poor infrastructure, regulatory inefficiencies, insecurity challenges, poor policies implementation and currency volatility continue to impact both FDI inflows and the non-oil export competitiveness. Although the non-oil exports steady Increase as it grew from ₦789 billion in 2000 to ₦4.5 trillion in 2023, reflecting efforts to diversify the economy.

This paper is aimed at providing a comprehensive analysis of the empirical and theoretical relationship between non-oil export sector growth and FDI in Nigeria with respect to the key trends.

By understanding the relationship between the two variables stakeholders can better design strategies to achieve economic diversification, reduce dependence on oil and foster inclusive growth in the country.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Export-Led Growth (ELG) and Early Foundations

The Export-Led Growth (ELG) theory argues that countries can stimulate economic growth by concentrating on the production and export of non-oil goods, thereby attracting foreign investment and enhancing competitiveness. According to Balassa (1978), export expansion contributes to economic growth through specialisation and comparative advantage. Similarly, Feder (1982) emphasised that export activities improve skills, enhance productivity, and encourage technology transfer, making exports an engine of growth.

2. FDI, Non-Oil Exports and Growth Linkages (1990s–2000s)

The Endogenous Growth Theory explains the role of foreign direct investment (FDI) in enhancing growth through technology transfer, knowledge spillovers, and skill development, provided the host country has sufficient absorptive capacity (Romer, 1990). Extending this view, Borensztein, De Gregorio, and Lee (1998) opined that FDI transfers technology and boosts productivity, especially when complemented by trade openness.

In the African context, Asiedu (2002) discovered that non-oil export orientation significantly determines FDI inflows, particularly when infrastructure and macroeconomic stability are present. Akinlo (2004) further argued that non-oil export performance enhances the benefits derived from FDI.

Ajayi (2006) expressed that Nigeria's weak infrastructure and poor educational system limit the extent to which FDI inflows benefit the non-oil export sector. Ogunleye (2008) added that diversifying into non-oil exports reduces Nigeria's vulnerability to external shocks, thereby creating a more attractive investment climate.

3. Empirical Evidence from Nigeria (2010s)

Ekperiwara (2011) advocated for greater encouragement of FDI in Nigeria's non-oil sector, noting that it yields more economic returns through human capital development, employment creation, and local content growth than the extractive sector dominated by expatriates.

Olayiwola and Okodua (2010) identified that non-oil exports positively impact economic growth, although policy inconsistency remains a major barrier. They also found a weak relationship between FDI and non-oil exports, largely attributed to institutional bottlenecks. Similarly, Okodua and Ewetan (2013) found a long-run relationship between non-oil exports and FDI, suggesting that strong export performance can attract more foreign investment. Anyanwu (2012) highlighted the importance of absorptive capacity, particularly the role of trade openness, regulatory quality, and financial market development in enhancing the benefits of FDI.

Amuko and Ekeudeka (2017) examined the effect of Nigeria's tax incentive policy, showing that it redirected foreign investment flows to the non-oil sector and contributed to its revival.

4. Recent Findings and Contemporary Evidence (2020s)

Aigheyisi and Iyoha (2020) found that while FDI positively affects non-oil industrial production in the short run, the effect becomes insignificant in the long run due to poor infrastructure and policy inconsistency. They further noted that financial development positively impacts non-oil industrial production, whereas inflation exerts adverse short- and long-term effects.

Recent studies reinforce the positive correlation between FDI and non-oil export growth but caution that the strength of this relationship is constrained by Nigeria's weak absorptive capacity. Policy inconsistency, corruption, and infrastructural decay continue to limit the efficiency of FDI in boosting non-oil exports.

Theoretically, Export-Led Growth (ELG) supports that increased non-oil exports in Nigeria indicates macroeconomic stability and openness, which attracts foreign investors. However, this can only be possible under the following conditions:

Improved trade infrastructure such as power, transport, road network, telecommunication etc. Consistent export policies through the introduction of efficient regulatory and institutional bodies to help achieve maximum exports result.

Encouraged Investment through friendly regulatory and corruption free system.

Reduced dependence on oil exports through the encouragement of linkage between FDI and local content value additions in non-oil export sectors.

Export led growth (ELG) theory is a principle whereby countries concentrate on the production and export of non-oil goods in order to develop their economy through the provision of conducive economic environment and to attract foreign investment into the country. This theory pinned that this strategy encourages higher productivity, technology transfer, economies of scale and competitiveness through international market participation. To this light it is agreed that export activities produce improved skills and allows technology transfer (Feder, 1982) and also lead to growth in economic resources due to specialisation and comparative advantage (Balassa, 1978).

Non-oil exports have been uncovered to have the potential to positively affect economic growth if infrastructure and policies consistency are improved. (Olayiwola and Okodua, 2010). In furtherance to this argument Ogunleye, (2008) suggested that diversification into non-oil exports can make Nigeria economy less vulnerable thereby creating a confidence economic environment for investors.

The relationship between non-oil export and foreign direct investment(FDI) is supposed to be a symbiosis relationship. This is where FDI stimulate non-oil exports by providing capital, technology and access to international markets, while in turn non-oil export can attract FDI

by indicating market potentials and policy stability. As such the role of FDI in transferring technology and boosting productivity, especially when supported by trade openness was expressed (Borensztein, De Gregorio and Lee, 1998). Also it was propounded that non-oil export orientation is a major determinant of FDI inflows in African economies, Nigeria inclusive. (Asiedu, 2002).

Also it was discovered that non-oil exports performance plays a major role in the increase in FDI benefits (Akinlo, 2004). Then in a research analysis of time series data a long run relationship between non-oil export and FDI suggesting that non-oil exports can as well attract more foreign investment when there are prospects (Okodua and Ewatan, 2013).

Ajayi (2006) in his study explained that Nigeria's poor infrastructure and weak educational system limit the benefits from FDI inflows to the non-oil export sectors.

Amuko J. and Ekeudeka F. (2017) opined that the tax incentive policy introduced changed the flow of foreign investment to the non-oil sector, showing that the country's tax incentives helped revive the ailing non-oil sector.

The Endogenous growth theory suggests that FDI can enhance economic growth through technology transfer, knowledge spill-over and skill development, if only the host country has adequate absorptive capacity (Romer, 1990). In furtherance, to this argument FDI inflows benefits countries with better infrastructure and macroeconomic stability – component of absorptive capacity (Asiedu, 2002). And on the other hand, Olayiwola and Okodua (2010) explain that a positive but weak relationship between FDI and non-oil exports is caused by institutional bottleneck thereby affecting the growth in FDI inflows. While the role of trade openness, regulatory institution efficiency and financial market development in enhancing Nigeria's absorptive capacity (Anyanwu, 2012).

Also the research work from C.M Ekperiware, (2011) strongly advise government and all stakeholders to encourage FDI into the non-oil sectors, it has more economic returns in the form of human capital, employment, local contents that the extractive sector dominated by expatriates. The local content policy should be strengthened more in the extractive industry to exploit the gains of that sector to economic growth.

The empirical evidence indicates that FDI positively and significantly affects non-oil industrial production in the short run and in the long run the effect is not very significant in the country. The short run and long run effects of FDI on non-oil industrial production are found to be statistically insignificant due to factors such as poor infrastructure, inconsistency in government policies etc. Financial development positively and significantly affects non-oil industrial production on the short-run and on the long-run. Further evidence is that inflation adversely affects non-oil industrial production on the short-run, as well as on the long-run according to Oziengbe Scott Aigheyisi² and Milton A. Iyoha, (2020).

Some studies show a positive correlation between FDI and non-oil export growth, the strength of the relationship is often limited by Nigeria's absorptive capacity, while few studies explicitly integrate the absorptive capacity framework into models assessing FDI-export linkages. However, there is a recurrent policy inconsistency, corruption, and poor infrastructure resulting to FDI inefficiency causing limitation to non-oil exports.

Theoretically, Export-Led Growth (ELG) supports that increased non-oil exports in Nigeria indicates macroeconomic stability and openness, which attracts foreign investors. However, this can only be possible under the following conditions:

Improved trade infrastructure such as power, transport, road network, telecommunication etc. Consistent export policies through the introduction of efficient regulatory and institutional bodies to help achieve maximum exports result.

Encouraged Investment through friendly regulatory and corruption free system.

Reduced dependence on oil exports through the encouragement of linkage between FDI and local content value additions in non-oil export sectors.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

Ho: Null Hypothesis is Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has impact on Non-oil export growth
 Hi: Alternate Hypothesis is Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has no impact on Non-oil export growth

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section of the paper elaborates on how data collection would be conducted. The data collection for this search work is the secondary data of non-oil exports, FDI inflow and GDP growth rate within 2000 to 2023 from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, data from National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) and World Bank – World Development Indicators (WDI). This data is free from manipulation since it is a data from reputable sources, no ethical concerns related to human subjects are involved.

The independent variable is Non-oil exports and dependent variable is Foreign Direct Investment, while the control variable is Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth rate.

Research Techniques

The data was analysed using econometric and statistical tools such as descriptive statistics to measure the mean, standard deviation, median, minimum and maximum value of each variable.

The correlation of the variables was measures using correlation coefficient to assess the linear relationship between non-oil exports and FDI.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test is applied on the variables to check the Stationarity of the variables and to examine whether the time series data is stationary or non-stationary. The data analysis was conducted using E-Views 12.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Table 1:

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS FOR TABLE OF FDI VS NON-OIL EXPORTS VS GDP – 2000 TO 2023

DESCRIPTION	FDI	NON-OIL EXPORT	GDP
Mean	18,557,384.43	895,295.37	1,758,464.23
Median	13,950,194.41	7,860.90	868,477.95
Standard Deviation	12,942,061.00	1,623,107.60	1,608,211.26
Minimum	3,432,490.05	789.00	329,178.70
Maximum	43,555,907.86	4,820,000.00	5,717,000.00
Skewness	0.50	1.70	1.22
Kurtosis	1.24	1.31	0.30
Count	24.00	24.00	24.00

From the above Table 1;

Studying the central tendency of the secondary data presented, it is noted that FDI, Non-oil exports and GDP have mean and median of N18,557,384.43 Billion, N895,295.37 Billion, N1,758,464.23 Billion and N13,950,194.41 Billion, N7,860.90 Billion, N868,477.95 Billion respectively. With all the mean value greater than the median this signify right skewness as indicated thus; FDI = 0.5, GDP = 1.22 and Non-oil export = 1.70.

However, the significant growth periods between 2016 and 2019 for the non-oil exports where substantial increase was recorded, indicated successful diversification strategies during that period.

The Standard deviation and Ranges are thus:

The three variables show large standard deviations, especially FDI and GDP, indicating **high variability** over the years;

- FDI Std. Dev = 12.94B

- GDP Std. Dev = 1.61B
- Non-Oil Export Std. Dev = 1.62B,
From Table 1; the Ranges are thus;
- **FDI:** 43.56B - 3.43B = **40.12B**
- **Non-Oil Export:** 4.82B - 789 = **~4.82B**
- **GDP:** 5.72B – 329M = **~5.39B**

For Kurtosis:

- **FDI:** -1.24 — platykurtic (flatter distribution, light tail or fewer outliers).
- **Non-Oil Export & GDP:** 1.30 and 0.30 respectively which is Slightly positive — closer to normal (mesokurtic). However, it is peaked, slightly heavy tails with more outliers.

For Skewness:

FDI and GDP have a skewness of 0.5 and 1.22 respectively, which is relatively positive and the FDI and GDP have relatively more consistent growth but still show positive skew (slightly right skewed)

While the non-oil exports which has a skewness of 1.70 is higher compared to FDI and GDP, and this is likely due to the sharp increase in some specific year such as 2019, 2021 – 2023. It is also right skewed too light GDP.

Generally, the distributions of the variables are not normal, as such other analysis should be conducted to enable proper confirmation of relationship between the variables.

In order to better understand the relationship between FDI, Non-oil exports and GDP the data could be better illustrated with histogram plot and line graph plot. Therefore, see below:

Graph 1a: Plot of Histogram Chart from Table 1:

FDI (Foreign Direct Investment):

- The distribution from the above histogram shows a **moderate right skew**, confirming the earlier skewness value (0.50).
- It is also noticed that most values are clustered on the lower end from 2010 - 2023, with fewer occurrences of high FDI inflows, while lower inflow is recorded from 2005 - 2008.
- The highest FDI according to the Table is 2023 record, while the lowest FDI is in 2005.

Graph 1b: line graph from Table 1

Non-Oil Export:

- The distribution of the values indicates **Strong right skew**, for the variable with a steep drop-off.
- It is noticed that most non-oil export values are low, while only a few years from 2017 – 2023 saw very high non-oil exports.
- We can agree the high skewness (1.70) and difference between mean and median is very high compared to the other variables.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP):

- Also indicate **right skew**, though slightly less extreme.
- The above chart Indicates that Nigeria had more years of moderate GDP for periods like 2000 – 2013 and fewer years of very high GDP from 2014 - 2019. This are the periods where the country recorded higher non-oil export growth.

Table 2:

Correlation Coefficient of FDI vs Non-oil export vs GDP from 2000 – 2023 – Eviews 12

Correlation Coefficient - Using Eviews 12			
Variables	FDI	Non-oil export	GDP
FDI	1.000000	0.180167	0.685029
Non-oil export	0.180167	1.000000	0.442271
GDP	0.685029	0.442271	1.000000

Summary of result:

Variables	Correlation Coefficient	Strength & Direction
FDI & GDP	0.6850	Moderate-Strong Positive
Non-Oil Export & GDP	0.4423	Moderate Positive
FDI & Non-Oil Export	0.1802	Weak Positive

From the summary, we can see that the Correlation Coefficient (r) for FDI and GDP is 0.6850 which mean the relationship is moderately strong positively, this translates that increase in foreign investment affects production, job creation and technology transfer. However, the correlation is **not perfect**, meaning there are other drivers apart from GDP that are significant in the relationship such as government revenues, local investment etc.

From the table, we can also notice the Correlation Coefficient (r) for Non-oil export and GDP is 0.4423 which mean the relationship is moderately positive, this translates that increase in non-oil export slightly affects production, while growth in non-oil exports growth on the other hand contributes also to employment generation, economic growth and infrastructural development, but to a lesser extent than FDI since the Nigeria economy is strongly financed by oil exports.

While the Correlation Coefficient (r) for FDI and Non-oil exports growth is 0.1802 which is very weak positively suggesting that FDI inflows are not significantly aligned with non-oil export growth possibly due to limited synergy between foreign investment and non-oil export capacity building, since FDI prefer to concentrated in **oil-export sectors** or **oil-related sectors** because of the high return on investment in the oil sector compared to the non-oil export sector. Therefore, foreign investors rather **prefer oil exports** than promoting **diversified exports**.

Summarily, Foreign Direct Investment has the strongest relationship with Gross Domestic Product among the three variables, whereas the non-oil exports show a modest contribution to economic growth. As such the Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) does not strongly influence non-oil exports, which is limited on return on investment and structural transformation in the non-oil sector.

Table 3: Granger Casualty Test:

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests
 Date: 07/08/25 Time: 19:29
 Sample: 2000 – 2023
 Lag: 2

		F-Statistics	Prob
Non-oil export does not Granger cause FDI	22	0.12021	0.8875
FDI does not Granger cause Non-oil export		3.72488	0.0455
GDP does not Granger cause FDI	22	0.01001	0.9900
FDI does not Granger cause GDP		0.77211	0.4776
GDP does not Granger cause Non-oil exports	22	1.02914	0.3788
Non-oil exports does not Granger cause GDP		2.51783	0.1102

1. FDI Granger-causes Non-Oil Export

From the above Table 3; we can notice that the P-value = 0.0455, as such it is less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis.

Implication:

From the Table 3 above Prob values of FDI signifies that it can be used to predict non-oil exports. This suggests that FDI has played a role in driving or enhancing export capacity in

non-oil sectors (e.g., agriculture, manufacturing). However, this can also play well if the government policy aligns with policy goals of attracting FDI to diversify exports.

2. Non-oil Export does not Granger-cause FDI

From the above Table 3; we identify that the P-value = 0.8875, meaning it is greater than 0.05, so we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Implication:

Referring to the Table 3 above, non-oil export performance does not influence future FDI inflows. This maybe as result that FDI is drawn more to the oil sector or due to international market potential, rather than being attracted by non-oil export due to government policies and the performance of the sector in terms of Pay Back Rate (PBR).

3. No Granger causality between GDP and FDI:

Studying the Table 3; we noticed that in both directions (GDP \rightarrow FDI and FDI \rightarrow GDP) the p-values (0.99 and 0.48) is higher than 0.05. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Implication:

This suggests that neither GDP growth nor FDI inflow cannot be used significantly to forecasts the other in this data. This invariably mean that either of the following or both: The Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) inflows may not be immediately productive when applied into the economy of the country, meaning there may be several pre-operational activities to handle before reasonable production can take place.

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth of the country is driven by other factors like oil exports, internal market potential, chain supply, government revenue etc.

4. No Granger causality between GDP and non-oil Export:

This mean that in both directions (GDP \rightarrow Non-oil export and Non-oil export \rightarrow GDP) the p-values (0.38 and 0.11) is higher than 0.05. Therefore, we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Implication:

It Implies that non-oil exports have not significantly influenced the GDP growth, and GDP growth has not boosted non-oil exports and it further confirms that non-oil exports remain a relatively weak component amongst the other variables in the economy such as oil export, government revenue, government policies etc.

For further test analysis on the variables FDI, Non-oil export growth and GDP relationship Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test is conducted on the time series data from 2000 to 2023 using E-views 12 and the results for the analysis at Level, 1st difference and 2nd difference is stated in the table below thus:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17593001>

Table 1: ADF Unit Root at Level												
LEVEL	Intercept						Trend and Intercept					
Variables	1%	5%	10%	ADF Test	Prob	Remarks	1%	5%	10%	ADF Test	Prob	Remarks
FDI	-3.7695	-	-	0.6889	0.9889	Non-stationary	-4.4407	-	-	-	0.5168	Non-stationary
Non-oil Export	-3.8573	-	-	-3.134	0.0419	Stationary	-4.5755	-	-	-	0.1512	Non-stationary
GDP	-3.7529	-2.998	-	-1.587	0.4732	Non-stationary	-4.5715	-	-	-	0.0050	Stationary

Table 2: ADF Unit Root at 1st Difference												
1st Difference	Intercept						Trend and Intercept					
Variables	1%	5%	10%	ADF Test	Prob	Remarks	1%	5%	10%	ADF Test	Prob	Remarks
FDI	-3.7695	-	-	-2.698	0.0903	Non-stationary	-4.4407	-	-	-	0.1052	Non-stationary
Non-oil Export	-3.8867	-	-	-1.569	0.4756	Non-stationary	-4.6162	-	-	-	0.8305	Non-stationary
GDP	-3.8867	-	-	-5.493	0.0004	Stationary	-4.6162	-	-	-	0.0002	Stationary

Table 2: ADF Unit Root at 2nd Difference												
2 nd Difference	Intercept											
Variables	1%	5%	10%	ADF Test	Prob	Remarks						

FDI	-3.7880	-	-	-5.529	0.0002	Stationary						
Non-oil Export	-3.9202	-	-	-0.330	0.8999	Non-stationary						
GDP	-3.9202	-	-	-3.509	0.0233	Stationary						

Studying the ADF Testing results using the standard ADF method, we test whether each series has a unit root (i.e. is non-stationary) at level and then at first difference. Going by the decision rule: If the ADF test statistic < critical value (more negative), reject H_0 (series is stationary) otherwise fail to reject.

For Null Hypothesis (H_0): Series has a unit root is it non-stationary.

Then for Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): Series is stationary.

Therefore, in summary of the analysis for the ADF test we have the following results:

@ Level

For the FDI: ADF value is 0.6889 which is greater than the critical value, so therefore the series has a unit root (i.e it is non-stationary).

For the Non-oil exports: ADF value is -3.1336 which is less than the critical value, so therefore the series has no unit root (i.e it is stationary).

For the GDP: ADF value is -1.5864 which is greater than the critical value, so therefore the series has a unit root (i.e it is non-stationary).

@ 1st difference

For the FDI: ADF value is -2.6977 which is greater than the critical value, so therefore the series has a unit root (i.e it is non-stationary).

For the Non-oil exports: ADF value is -1.5697 which greater than the critical value, so therefore the series has a unit root (i.e it is non-stationary).

For the GDP: ADF value is -5.4930 which is less than the critical value, so therefore the series has no unit root (i.e it is stationary).

@ 2nd difference

For the FDI: ADF value is -5.5298 which is less than the critical value, so therefore the series has no unit root (i.e it is stationary).

For the Non-oil exports: ADF value is -0.3301 which greater than the critical value, so therefore the series has a unit root (i.e it is non-stationary).

For the GDP: ADF value is -3.5 which is less than the critical value, so therefore the series has no unit root (i.e it is stationary).

So we can notice that @ level it is only Non-oil export that is stationary.

And @ 1st difference it is only GDP that is stationary, while @ 2nd difference it is both FDI and GDP that are stationary.

Invariably, all the three variables show unit roots at levels meaning their statistical properties (mean, variance) change over time, and as such one of the variable cannot easily be used to predict the other variables as it could be misleading. However, they become stationary after second differencing, which is typical for macroeconomic variables, which may be as a result of either inflation, growth rate changes or policies changes or inconsistencies.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Since non-oil exports contribute significantly to GDP growth, at the rate of 1.46% increase per GDP to 1% non-oil export promoting diversification remains crucial to every economy. However, the recent decline in FDI requires the need to assess the situation and possibly

improve the investment environment to attract and retain foreign investors as previous years from 2015 to 2021.

However, the hypothesis testing indicates that FDI has impact or influences the growth in the Non-oil sectors, but the change is not very significant due to other profitable attractive sectors like the oil export sector, telecommunication sector, etc. This conclusion is due to the P-value = 0.0455, which is less than 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis.

But, past reports of FDI can be used to predict non-oil exports growth to some extent, which suggests that FDI has played a role in driving or enhancing export capacity in non-oil sectors (e.g., agriculture, manufacturing), but unless this aligns with policy goals of attracting FDI to diversify non-oil exports as implemented by the then President Goodluck Abele Jonathan regime.

Despite the long-term growth recorded in past years, recently reports indicate a decline in FDI; when in 2024, FDI fell by 42.3% to \$1.08 billion, suggesting potential investor concerns or shifts in the investment climate due to government economic policies. Therefore, it is important that the government address these issue through the following macroeconomic strategies as thus:

1. Strengthen the Link Between Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and the Non-Oil Sector

Government should initiate or develop targeted investment incentives to channel Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) into non-oil industrial sectors like agriculture, manufacturing, ICT, and services in order to grow the sector.

Create export processing zones (EPZs) or special economic zones (SEZs) with infrastructures that will specially provide enabling and easy production environment or reduce cost of production, in order to attract FDI into export-oriented sectors and also backed by logistics, financing, and quality assurance.

2. Boost Non-Oil Export Capacity

Government should Improve infrastructure, especially transport and logistics, to reduce cost of production as well as cost of export of non-oil products. In addition, Government should provide financial and technical support to small and medium enterprises (SMEs) involved in non-oil exports, they should provide condition that will encourage value-added processing of raw materials (e.g., cocoa, cotton, solid minerals) to increase export value.

3. Encourage Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) for Sustainable Economic Growth

The government should creation of enabling environment for technology and knowledge transfer from foreign firms to local industries through collaboration and partnership.

Government should strengthen investment regulations to align FDI with national economic development goals as well as improve the ease of doing business by reducing unnecessary bottleneck procedures and reduce corruption to sustain investor confidence by introducing monitoring agencies to check excesses of stakeholders as well as promote transparency and consistency in economic and trade policy

4. Diversify Gross Domestic Product (GDP) Drivers

Reduce over-reliance on oil by diversifying the economic base through the introduction of tax rebate for non-oil export sectors.

Encourage domestic investments alongside FDI to promote inclusive growth through the introduction of collaborative activities between foreign investors and locals.

5. Capitalise on FDI's Predictive Role in Non-Oil Export Growth

Introduce Incentives to Foreign Investor in export-oriented non-oil sectors through tax holidays, trade facilitation, and infrastructure support.

Encourage technology transfer and skills development from foreign firms to local producers through partnerships and introduction of trade policies and agreements to open new markets for Nigerian non-oil exports.

6. Creation of Stable National Currency

Currency stabilisation through the implementation of the right macroeconomic policies by the government to keep the non-oil exports competitive.

However, this research work can be further extended in order to uncover other challenges and come up with possible solution in area such as using dynamic panel models, structural VARs, or ARDL models that incorporate absorptive capacity variable such as infrastructure, education, skills and innovation indices.

Investigate **time lags** and indirect channels through which FDI and exports might impact GDP.

Combine Granger causality with **VAR/VECM models** for deeper dynamic insights.

Focus on strategies to grow and stabilize non-oil exports and FDI—both boost GDP growth and support economic resilience.

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